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Influence of plant growth regulators on carbon/nitrogen metabolism of cucumber under salt stress

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ABSTRACT: This study was designed with the objective of comparing three different plant growth regulators, putrescine (Put), meta-topolin (mT), and 24-epibrassinolide (EBL), in affecting cucumber plants under salt stress. The pilot assessment revealed that all treatments had a significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on vegetative traits, seedling vigor, total chlorophyll content, and root activity compared to control. The treatment T5 showed the greatest numbers in regard to the above-mentioned traits compared with other combinations. The salt stress study reported that T2 increased superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD), catalase (CAT), and ascorbate peroxidase (APX) activities in leaves by 31%, 4.4%, 22.4%, and 35.2%, respectively, in comparison with the control. On the other hand, S3 markedly increased antioxidant enzyme activities, and the activity level was significantly higher than the control and salt treatment. Exogenous S3 had a highly significant effect on glutamine synthetase (GS), glutamate synthase (GOGAT), and (GDH), glutamate dehydrogenase activities in leaves and roots compared with T2. Application of S3 had a highly significant effect on sucrose synthase (SS) and sucrose phosphate synthase (SPS) under salinity stress in leaves and roots compared with other salt stress treatments. The results showed that (5 mM Put + 0.002 ppm mT + 0.001 ppm EBR) treatment alleviated the growth inhibition caused by salt stress by regulating the C-N enzyme activities in cucumber plants.

Keywords: Putrescine; Meta-topolin; 24-Epibrassinolide.

1. INTRODUCTION

Plant development and biomass production are basically connected to the interdependent regulation of carbon-nitrogen (C-N) assimilation because C and N work as critical key nutrients during plant growth [1]. Nitrogen plays important roles in vegetable growth, especially cucumber because it is a part of plant amino acids, the building blocks of protein; it is well known that N forms critical portions of chlorophyll molecules, several other metabolites, and cellular components [2]. The requirement for great amounts of N in plant crops largely reveals the N used in their photosynthetic apparatus, which combines CO₂, H₂O₂, and N into sugars and

amino acids, the basic building blocks of biomass accumulation [3]. Hence, nitrogen availability is vital for both increasing adequate photosynthetic capacity to convert the light energy into chemical energy [4, 5] and improving plant growth especially under stressful conditions [6-8]. On the other hand, adaptation of N wants energy and carbon skeletons, which are delivered by C compounds counting several carbohydrates (in particular sucrose (Suc) fructose (Fru). and glucose (Glu); [1], especially when nitrate NO_3^- serves as the main form of N. In vegetable plants, nitrate (NO_3^-) is reduced to ammonium (NH_4^+). The NH_4^+ is then assimilated to create glutamine, or alternatively, NH_4^+ is used in the glutamate [9]. These important processes need high energy and reducing equivalents, which are created by photosynthesis. Thus, photosynthesis plays a critical role in the N assimilation process, although this role may be direct or indirect. As such, the interaction between photosynthesis C and N metabolism is very important in achieving plant optimal growth and development [1, 10].

Salt stress conditions affect the diverse steps of nitrogen metabolism, such as uptake, reduction, and protein synthesis, which may be responsible, at least in part, for the reduced plant growth vigor observed in such conditions. Salt stress can disturb the intercellular C and N homeostasis of higher plant cells, which leads to a diminution of metabolic activity and finally reduces plant growth and development [1, 11, 12].

Plant growth regulators (PGRs) are certainly produced by plants and can regulate plant metabolism, growth parameters, and improvement under normal and stressful conditions. These PGRs are created in different plant organs, inside the plant the PGRs move until they bind to receptors and trigger reactions in cells [13, 14]. PGRs affect cell processes such as cell division and elongation and can improve plants against stress conditions [15]. By adding PGRs we can control the plant processes such as the formation and growth of roots, shoots, buds, flowers, and fruits [14, 16]. One study, showed the role of interaction between putrescine (PAs), and 24-epibrassinolide (EBR), in the enhancement of radish growth under Cu stress [17]. Other study, investigated EBR and/or Put trigger physiological and biochemical responses for the salt stress mitigations in *Cucumis sativus* L. The possible interaction of more than two PGRs in plants under stress condition is still an area lake explore [20]. A previous study, concluded that the application of 5 mM L⁻¹ Put + 0.02 ppm L⁻¹mT + 0.001 mg L⁻¹ EBR can be used to modify coco-peat substrate with a positive effect on plant growth and improvement of cucumber plants under unstressed conditions [18]. Hence, this study aims to investigate the interaction for Put, mT and EBR in enhancing total nitrogen, yield, fruit qualities and C-N enzyme activities in cucumber under NaCl.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this investigation, two studies were carried out at Soilless Culture Department, Institute of Vegetables and Flowers (IVF), Chinese Academy of Agriculture Science (CAAS), Beijing, China. The Cucumber cultivar Zhong Nong No 26 (F1) was used as a test material. Seeds were placed in Petri dishes (9×9 cm) on filter paper moistened with sterile water and incubated for approximately 24 hours at $28 \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$. Thereafter, germinated seeds were cultivated in the trays after the incubation period until they became 2 true leaves. Then, plantlets were transferred to plastic containers (50×70 cm) placed in the greenhouse after being filled with coco-peat substrate. The substrate was washed five times with tap water before use.

2.1. Pilot assessment study

The study was laid out in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications and 5 pots for each treatment. Randomly 3 plants were selected to determine the vegetative growth parameters. The seedlings were treated with plant growth regulators combinations PGRsc at different percentages from each one

(0%, 50% and 100%) for all of putrescin, meta-topolin and 24-epibrassinolide. Putrescin levels were 0% = 0 mM, 50% = 5 mM, and 100% = 10 mM/L; Meta-topolin levels were 0% = 0 ppm, 50% = 0.01 ppm and 100% = 0.02 ppm/L and 24-Epibrassinolide levels were 0% = 0 mg/L, 50% = 0.0005 mg/L and 100% = 0.001 mg/L during April 2018. Consequently, nine PGRsc treatments were generated from these combinations. PGRsc were mixed with coco-peat substrate first out of the containers and then seedlings were transplanted in the containers on the same day. The used treatments in the current investigation are listed in (Table 1).

Table 1. The combinations of plant growth regulators Put, mT and EBL which used in the current study.

Treatments	Putrescin (Put) mM/L	Meta-topolin (mT) ppm/L	24-Epibrassinolide (EBL) mg/L
T1 (control)	0	0	0
T2	5	0.01	0.0005
T3	5	0.01	0.001
T4	5	0.02	0.0005
T5	5	0.02	0.001
T6	10	0.01	0.0005
T7	10	0.01	0.001
T8	10	0.02	0.0005
T9	10	0.02	0.001

Vegetative growth parameters were measured after 30 days from treatments i.e. plant height (m), stem diameter (mm), leaf number, leaf area (cm²), shoot fresh weight (g), shoot dry weight (g), root fresh weight (g), root dry weight (g). Seedlings vigor index (SVI) was determined using the seedling vigor index (SVI) indicator [18]. Seedling vigor index was calculated after 4 weeks as; $SVI = [\text{stem thickness (cm)}/\text{seedling length (cm)} + \text{root fresh weight (g)}/\text{shoot fresh weight (g)}] \times [\text{shoot fresh weight (g)} + \text{root fresh weight (g)}]$. Chlorophyll content was measured using a chlorophyll meter (SPAD-502, Konica Minolta Sensing Inc Japan).

2.2. Root activity

Measurement of root was performed according to the TTC method [19]. The substrate was removed from the root using tweezers, and then the roots were washed with sterile water. The surface liquid of roots was blotted with tissue paper and their fresh weights were measured. Roots with weights 0.5 g were placed in tubes and filled with 5 ml of 0.4% TTC and 5 ml phosphate buffer (0.06 mol/L, pH 7.0). Control treatment (blank runs) was always carried out using the same procedure but adding 2 ml of 1 mol/L–1 sulfuric acid first. The tubes were incubated at 37° C for up to 4 hr. The chemical reaction was stopped by adding 2 ml of 1 mol/L sulfuric acid into the tubes. This step followed by extraction with 10 ml of 95% ethanol for 24 h, which consisted of taking the root in a new tube. The optical density (OD) values were recorded at 485 nm.

$$\text{Root activity } (\mu\text{g/g FW/h}) = (\text{OD} + 0.0035) / (\text{h} \times \text{w} \times 0.0022)$$

where, OD = optical density; h = 4 hours; w = 0.5 g.

2.3. Salt stress experiment

This study was executed in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications and 5 pots for each treatment. Randomly sample was selected to determine the parameters. The experiment was conducted with 3 treatments as follow: S1- nutrient solution, control (CK); S2 - 80 mM NaCl and S3 - 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 mg EBL + 80 mM NaCl.

2.4. Morphological parameters

The shoots and roots were sampled 90 days after the beginning of the treatment and were then washed with deionized water, with subsequent topical removal of the surface water with tissue paper. After determining fresh weight, cucumber shoots and roots were placed in the air and dried to determine the dry weight.

2.5. Determination of early fruit yield and quality parameters

2.5.1. Early fruit yield

Fruit yield (g)/plant was calculated from the number of fruits per plant multiplied by fruit weights per plant.

2.5.2. Electro-leakage and protein content

Total inorganic ions leaked out of the leaves were estimated as described: twenty leaf discs were taken in a boiling test tube containing 10 ml deionized water, and electrical conductivity was measured (ECa). The tubes were heated at 45°C and 55°C for 30 min in a water bath, and electrical conductivity was measured (ECb) each time. Later, the contents were again boiled at 100°C for 10 min, and electrical conductivity was again recorded (ECc) [20]. The electrolyte leakage was calculated using the formula:

Electrolyte leakage (%) = $ECb - Eca \div ECc \times 100$.

Protein content of samples was determined by the Bradford reagent [21] prepared as follows: Fresh leaves (0.5 g) were ground, homogenized in 10 ml of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) in an ice bath, and centrifuged at 6000g for 5 min at 4 °C. To the supernatant (0.1 ml) and 2 ml of Bradford reagent was added and the mixture was kept for 5 min at room temperature. The absorbance was read at 595 nm using a spectrophotometer (UV-1800, Shimadzu). Protein content was calculated by formula: Protein content = $V \times VT / VS \times WF \times 100$ Where, C: for the standard curve, VT: total vol. of the extracted liquid, VS: for the added specimen during measurement, WF: for weight of the sample.

2.5.3. Malondialdehyde, proline, and antioxidant enzymes in leaves

Malondialdehyde (MDA), proline, superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD), catalase (CAT) and ascorbate peroxidase (APX) were determined by kits purchased from Solarbio Science & Technology Co., Ltd, Beijing, <http://www.solarbio.com>.

2.5.4. Nitrogen and carbon enzymes in leaves and roots

The glutamine synthetase (GS), glutamate synthase (GOGAT), glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH), sucrose synthase (SS), and sucrose phosphate synthase (SPS), were determined by kits purchased from Solarbio Science & Technology Co., Ltd, Beijing, <http://www.solarbio.com>.

2.5.5. Vitamin C (AsA), soluble sugar in fruits

To estimate cucumber fruit quality under different treatments. Fresh fruit samples of cucumber in each plot were collected when daily fruit production was very high, and their appearance should be similar and marketable. Fresh fruits were washed, chopped and mixed in the lab to assess different quality indexes.

Vitamin C After harvest, the samples were immediately stored at -80°C before analysis. Five-gram samples were homogenized until uniform consistency in a meta-phosphoric acid and acetic acid solution. This solution was used for the ascorbic acid extraction after quantitative reduction of 2, 2-dichlorophenolindophenol dyestuff by ascorbic acid and extraction of the excess dyestuff using xylene. The excess of ascorbic acid was measured at 500 nm in a spectrophotometer and compared with a vitamin C reference standard (ISO/6557-2-

1984 method) [22].

Soluble sugar content was determined by anthrone ethyl acetate colorimetric. Briefly, fruit samples (2 g) were homogenized in water (20 mL) and centrifuged at 13,500 rpm until uniform consistency. The absorbance was measured at 630 nm in a spectrophotometer.

2.5.6. Total nitrogen in leaves

Leaf tissue was taken during the harvest after the last applications and then oven-dried at 68 °C for 48 h and ground to pass through a 1-mm mesh screen. Accurately weighed samples; of 0.5 g of the dried ground materials were subjected to wet digestion using a mixture of sulfuric acid and hydrogen peroxide. The Kjeldahl method and a Vapodest 10 Rapid Kjeldahl distillation unit (Gerhardt, Konigs winter, Germany) were used to determine the total N [23].

2.6. Statistical analysis

This study was laid out in Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replicates and 7 pots for each treatment. We selected randomly 7 plants to determine all parameters. The data were analyzed statistically using Costas version 8.1 software. The differences among means were compared with Tukey's test at level $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Pilot experiment

Exogenous application of plant growth regulators combinations PGRsc Put + mT + EBL significantly improved cucumber growth parameters. The treated seedlings with 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 mg EBL (T5), resulted highly significant increase in all plant growth factors compared with the control. The increase in plant height, leaf numbers, leaf area, stem diameter, shoot fresh, shoot dry weight, root fresh and root dry weight was estimated to be 46.6%, 38.2%, 70.7%, 47.4%, 71.5%, 85.3%, 76.5% and 71.5% respectively by T5 compared with control (Table 2 & 3).

Table 2. Means of plant height, leaf numbers leaf area and stem diameter for cucumber seedlings grown on coco-peat substrate mixed with PGRsc.

Treatments	Plant. h(m)	Leaf No.	Leaf area(cm ²)	Stem dia.(mm)
T1	1.31 e	7.89 g	38.56 e	2.57 e
T2	1.71 d	8.78 f	38.75 c.	2.99 cde
T3	1.95 b	10.33 c	101.77 bc	3.71 b
T4	2.00 ab	12.00 b	124.00 a	4.52 a
T5	2.06 a	12.78 a	132.03 a	4.89 a
T6	1.85 c	9.78 d	111.76 ab	3.51 bc
T7	1.96 b	10.56 c	116.06 ab	3.88 b
T8	1.82 c	9.33 e	96.83 bc	3.40 cde
T9	1.63 d	8.56 f	58.08 d	2.89 de

Values followed by the same letters are not significantly at 0.05 levels.

Table 3. Means of shoot fresh weight, shoot dry weight, root fresh weight and root dry weight for cucumber seedlings grown on coco-peat substrate mixed with PGRsc.

Treatment	Shoot. FW/g	Shoot. DW/g	Root. FW/g	Root. DW/g
T1	37.60 h	5.28 f	8.35 g	2.13 e
T2	55.98 f	7.93 ef	11.37 ef	2.88 d
T3	107.27 d	14.77 d	13.07 d	3.53 cdc
T4	130.13 a	35.33 a	34.88 a	7.05 a
T5	132.13 a	36.02 a	35.62 a	7.48 a
T6	120.33 b	29.03 b	22.38 b	3.52 c
T7	115.60 c	24.72 c	18.22 c	3.67 c
T8	93.22 e	9.67 e	12.10 e	3.35 c
T9	47.88 g	7.73 f	10.95 d f	2.47 e

Values followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 0.05 levels.

Figure 1. Effect of PGRsc on cucumber root seedlings growth after 30 days.

3.2. Seedlings vigor index (SVI)

Regarding the seedlings Vigor index (SVI), the seedlings treated with T5 had the greatest SVI compared to other combinations and it was highly significant compared with the control. The increase in cucumber SVI was 77.4% by T5 compared with control treatment T1. All other treatments increased SVI in comparison with control (Fig. 2a).

3.3. Chlorophyll content (SPAD)

Application of T5 on cucumber plants showed the highest chlorophyll content 74.42 (SPAD unit) as compared with all treatments. The other PGRsc treatments showed significant results regarding chlorophyll content compared with control (Fig. 2b).

3.4. Root activity

Cucumber root activity had a highly significant effect by using different treatments. The maximum root activity was observed with T5 which recorded 396.70 ug/g.fw.h respectively. On the other hand, the data from T1 revealed a minimum root activity of 138.5 ug/g.fw.h (Fig. 2c).

3.5. Electrolyte leakage

In Fig. 3a, the treatment with 80 mM NaCl, induced significant increases in electrolyte leakage compared to control. The application of 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 mg EBL + 80 mM NaCl, lowered

electrolyte leakage compared to sole salt stress treatment. The highest electro leakage value observed when the cucumber seedlings exposed to 80 mM NaCl was recorded 23.7 compared with unstressed plants, while electro leakage value reduced to be 18.7 when the plants exposed to 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 mg EBL + 80 mM NaCl.

Figure 2. Effect of PGRsc on cucumber seedlings vigor (SVI), chlorophyll content, and seedlings roots activity. Vertical bars denoted the SD; columns in the figure that are headed with different letters are significantly different at $P < 0.05$.

3.6. Soluble protein content

Soluble protein content was significantly reduced in cucumber leaves under salt stress treatment. The lowest soluble protein contents, recorded 6.2 mg/fw, in the leaves by 80 mM NaCl. Exogenous 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 mg EBL + 80 mM NaCl, markedly increased soluble protein content in the plants, and the activity levels were significantly higher than the treatment with 80 mM NaCl and it is recorded 13.9 mg/fw (Fig. 3b).

3.7. Proline content

Proline content was significantly increased in cucumber leaves under salt stress treatment. And it is recorded 2264.9 $\mu\text{g/g}$ fw by 80 mM NaCl. Exogenous 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 mg EBL + 80 mM NaCl, markedly increased proline content in cucumber plants, and the activity level was significantly higher than the treatments with 80 mM NaCl and it recorded 2857.6 $\mu\text{g/g}$ fw (Fig. 3c).

Figure 3. Effect of PGRsc on cucumber electro leakage, soluble protein content, proline, MDA, SOD, POD, CAT, and APX under salt stress. Vertical bars denoted the SD; columns in the figure that are headed with different letters are significantly different at $P < 0.05$.

3.8. Malondialdehyde (MDA) content

Our result showed that Malondialdehyde (MDA) contents increased significantly under salt stress condition T2 compared with control. While MDA significantly decreased by using T3 compared with salt stress alone (Fig. 3d).

3.9. Antioxidant enzyme activities

The superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD), catalase (CAT) and ascorbate peroxidase (APX) activities in cucumber seedlings leaves had increased during the exposure to salt stress by 31, 4.4, 22.4% and 35.2% respectively, in comparison with the control. Exogenous 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 mg EBL, markedly increased antioxidant enzyme activities in salt-stressed plants, and the activity levels had significantly higher than the control and salt treatment. While the application of 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 mg EBL, had no obvious effects on APX activities under salt stress (Fig. 3e, f, g, i and h).

3.10. Plant biomass

The data is presented in (Figure 4). Showed that shoot fresh weight, shoot dry weight, root fresh weight and root dry weight in cucumber plants decreased significantly under salt stress condition S2 compared with control. While shoot fresh weight, shoot dry weight, root fresh weight and root dry weight significantly increased by using S3 compared with salt stress alone.

Figure 4. Effect of Put, mT and EBR on cucumber (a) shoot fresh and (b) shoot dry weight (c) root fresh and (d) root dry weight under salt stress. Vertical bars denoted the SD; columns in the figure that are headed with different letters are significantly different according to LSD test at $P < 0.05$.

3.11. Early fruit yield

The data presented in (Fig. 5) revealed that early fruit yield in cucumber plants decreased significantly under salt stress condition S2 compared with control. On the other hand, early fruit yield significantly increased by using S3 compared with salt stress.

Figure 5. Effect of Put, mT and EBR on early yield under salt stress in cucumber plant. Vertical bars denoted the SD; columns in the figure that are headed with different letters are significantly different according to LSD test at $P < 0.05$.

3.12. Vitamin C (AsA)

Seedlings subjected to NaCl stress showed a significant decrease in the AsA content of cucumber fruits when compared with the control. PGRsc applied was observed to enhance AsA significantly under NaCl compared with salt stress alone (Fig. 6).

3.13. Total soluble sugar

Data illustrated in (Fig. 6) indicated that the soluble sugar in cucumber fruits was affected under the different treatments compared with S2. Total soluble sugar significantly increased with S3 treatment. On the other hand, soluble sugar in cucumber fruits significantly decreased in comparison with salt stress alone.

3.14. Total nitrogen

The data presented in (Fig. 6) showed that nitrogen content in cucumber leaves decreased significantly under salt stress condition S2 compared with control. While nitrogen content significantly increased by using S3 compared with salt stress alone.

Figure 6. Effect of Put, mT and EBR on AsA content, total soluble sugar and total nitrogen under salt stress in cucumber leaves. Vertical bars denoted the SD; columns in the figure that are headed with different letters are significantly different according to LSD test at $P < 0.05$.

3.15. Nitrogen enzyme activities in leaves and roots

In regard to nitrogen enzymes the GS and GOGAT activities decreased significantly in cucumber NaCl stress. Exogenous application of 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 ppm EBR, was highly effective for

enhancing the GS and GOGAT activities in conjunction with 80 mM NaCl stress (Fig. 6). On the contrary, under 80 mM NaCl stress, GDH activity increased significantly as compared with the Control. Nevertheless, the application of S3, to the plants showed a high significant effect on the GDH activity of cucumber leaves and roots (Fig. 7).

Figure 7. Effect of Put, mT and EBR on GS enzyme activities in (a) leaves and (b) roots, GOGAT enzyme activities (c) leaves and (d) roots, and GDH enzyme activities under salt stress in cucumber (e) leaves and (f) roots. Vertical bars denoted the SD; columns in the figure that are headed with different letters are significantly different according to LSD test at P < 0.05.

3.16. Carbohydrate enzymes in leaves and roots

The SPS activities in both leaves and roots were significantly increased in cucumber under NaCl stress compared with the control. Exogenous application of 5 mM Put + 0.02 ppm mT + 0.001 ppm EBR significantly decreased SPS under 80 mM NaCl stress. On the contrary, under 80 mM NaCl stress, SS activities increased significantly as compared with the Control. Nevertheless, the application of S3, to the plants showed high significant decreased in SS activities of cucumber leaves and roots (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Effect of Put, mT and EBR on SPS enzyme activities under salt stress in cucumber (a) leaves and (b) roots, and SS enzyme activities under salt stress in cucumber (c) leaves and (d) roots. Vertical bars denoted the SD; columns in the figure that are headed with different letters are significantly different according to LSD test at $P < 0.05$.

4. DISCUSSION

Obtained results in this work showed that cucumber seedlings treated with exogenous PGRsc via roots were better able to adapt to NaCl stress, as reflected by a significant increase of cucumber root fresh and dry weights as well as total nitrogen. It is reported that stress tolerance helps plants to survive under stressed conditions. The root is considered to be a vital organ system of plants due to their involvement in water and nutrient acquisition, storage functions, metabolite synthesis and accumulation. It is the first organ to suffer from excess salinity and the primary site of salinity perception. Thus, the maintenance of root growth is essential for coping with NaCl stress. Another suggestion is that using of PGRs modified the pH buffering capacity (pHBC), total organic carbon (TOC), organic matter (OM), cation exchange capacity (CEC), and nutrient storage capacity especially NH_4^+ around roots [24].

In the salt stress experiment our results showed that NaCl-induced MDA content in cucumber leaves and using of PGRsc reduced significantly the MDA under NaCl. The reduction of MDA by PGRsc is one of the most important mechanisms in improving plants against stress and it may be due to alleviating salt-induced oxidative damage to the membranes [25]. PGRsc submission could powerfully protect the structural integrity of the membranes resulting in the improvement of salt tolerance. The salinity stress increased SOD, POD, CAT and APX activities as also proline content of our results within agreement with [12, 26-28]. The increase in antioxidant enzyme activities and proline content may be the result of the protective mechanism [27]. In this study, PGRsc increased the activities of SOD and POD and CAT in cucumber under salt stress. It has been reported that PGRsc improved cucumber antioxidant enzyme activities as well as that of proline content by

using PGRsc. However, PGRsc had no obvious effects on APX activity [26]. The results indicated that the effects of PGRsc on the antioxidant enzymes as well as proline content were very complex, and the mechanisms of PGRsc-mediated resistance to oxidative stress still require further studies.

The improvement of cucumber growth under normal and stress conditions by using plant growth regulators combination is due to alterations in the phenotypes of plants and affects growth either by enhancing or by stimulating the natural growth regulatory systems from seed germination to senescence [28, 29]. Our suggestion is that maybe PGRsc modified the respiratory process by inducing soluble sugar and vitamin C content in cucumber seedlings which leads to good feedback plant growth under normal and stressful conditions. Plant growth regulators can promote gene expression activates of several enzymes complicated with the tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA), as previously observed in maize plants treated with plant growth regulators [30]. The new study [22] stated that soluble sugar increased in pepper fruits by using organic PGRs when soluble sugar translocated from leaves to fruits at the maturity stage. The increased accumulation of sugars is strongly associated with the level of ascorbic acid. One study accomplished on the ascorbate-deficient mutant of *Arabidopsis thaliana* delivered indication that the ascorbic acid biosynthetic pathway starts from glucose, thus emphasizing a positive relationship between ascorbic acid and sugar levels in plants [22]. Increased levels of ascorbic acid were also observed in tomato plants treated with PGRs [25]. The cucumber plant is a good source of ascorbic acid as an antioxidant compound, which is extremely involved in the high level of light capture and in the reduction of oxidative stress. The effect of PGRsc on soluble sugar and vitamin C in cucumber needs more investigation under normal and salinity stress conditions.

Our study showed that 80 mM NaCl stress strongly limits plant production [31]. The study suggests that salt stress is the major environmental limiting factor for plant growth and development [27, 32-37] reported that Salinity can alter the plant metabolisms, like osmotic adjustment, ion uptake, protein, photosynthesis, organic solutes accumulation, enzyme activity, tissue injury, and reduced water availability to crop plants. High salt stress can develop a nutrient imbalance in plants [4, 38, 39]. However, the application of exogenous S3 could alleviate the inhibition of plant growth in response to NaCl stress. The effect induced by S3 on the growth of the salt-stressed cucumber might involve the regulation of carbohydrate production and N assimilation mechanisms [40-42]. PGRs are used to enhance fruit color, suppress plant overgrowth, promote flower differentiation, protect flowers and fruit, accelerate fruit ripening and promote the production of seedless fruits [43]. The application of PGRs can also be used to increase yields and make crops available for market during the off-season [44].

Our study showed that using PGRsc under salt stress induced nitrogen enzymes (GS/GOGAT), activates and assimilation. Our investigation suggests that once nitrogen enzymes catalyze the conversion of NO_3^- to NO_2^- , the NO_2^- will be reduced to NH_4^+ . While it is commonly believed that more than 95% of the NH_4^+ in higher plants is assimilated via the GS/GOGAT pathway, some have debated that GDH could contribute to ammonium NH_4^+ assimilation to a certain extent [45, 46]. This type of reaction could occur when the NH_4^+ content in a plant cell is increased considerably or as a result of metabolic alarms caused by salt stress [47, 48]. In the present study, GDH activity increased significantly under NaCl stress, and a further increase was induced by the application of PGRsc. This suggests that the activation of GDH mainly contributes to the replenishment of leaf glutamate, an amino acid that plays central signaling and metabolic roles at the interface of the C and N assimilatory pathway and acts as a C and N source for the biosynthesis of most other amino acids [49, 50]. Our suggestion is that produced by the GS/GOGAT and/or GDH pathway, can be directly converted Glutamate (Glu), to proline (Pro) or indirectly into putrescine (Put) [51]. Therefore, PAs and Pro biosynthesis share several

substrates. Exogenous PGRsc could modulate the endogenous polyamine content that shifted more substrates for Pro biosynthesis [52], in response to NaCl stress. The substantial accumulation of Pro by exogenous PGRsc acts as a protectant and protein stabilizer for cell membranes contributes to the stabilization of subcellular structures and improves the cell water status in a way that alleviates osmotic pressure under NaCl-induced osmotic stress [53]. In addition, Pro served as a free radical scavenger and a source of C and showed a positive role in maintaining photosynthetic activity and improving plant growth under NaCl stress [54, 55]. Therefore, exogenous PGRsc could effectively regulate the GS, GOGAT and GDH activities to speed up the conversion of NH_4^+ to Glu and Pro, which are the precursors of other amino acids and help alleviate the NaCl stress.

To maintain normal growth under salinity, plants need to regulate carbon allocation, partitioning and its use in the sink organs [56-60]. C and N metabolism are highly interconnected; the incorporation of inorganic N into organic compounds requires the availability of energy and C skeletons, which are provided by the respiration of carbohydrates. This is especially so when nitrate is the major source of nitrogen. Hence, it is important to ensure that there is enough C diverted to produce C skeletons which are needed during the assimilation [2, 15, 58, 61, 62].

Sucrose synthase (SS), and sucrose phosphate synthase (SPS), regulated sucrose metabolism in plants [63]. SS plays a central role in the secondary metabolism of sucrose. When plants are subjected to chilling, drought, and salt stress, SS will catalyze the synthesis of sucrose by using glucose and fructose as substrates. However, this catalytic process is reversible, which means SS also could decompose sucrose into glucose and fructose [64, 65]. In this study the activities of SS and SPS increased with salt stress and decreased with PGRsc application to NaCl because of the function of SS in catalyzing both sucrose synthesis and degradation, our study agreement with [64, 65]. The difference between SS and SPS is that SPS is located in the cytoplasm, only catalyzes sucrose synthesis and is involved in the most critical synthetic route of sucrose in higher plants. Additionally, SPS is widely implicated in many stress response mechanisms [66].

Our study suggests that the stress system may negatively affect the maintenance of the balance among sucrose production, translocation, partition and uses are important for the normal growth of plants our findings within agreement with [67-69]. The disturbance of sucrose in leaves may have caused an increase sucrose levels in the roots and might have been due to a higher sucrose synthesis than degradation, and maybe glucose and fructose levels increased under salt conditions and this increase might have been attributed to the increases in the activities of SS. On the other hand, using S3 caused a significant decrease of SPS and SS compared with salt stress. These results suggested that the PGRsc alleviated NaCl stress and regulated carbohydrate enzyme activities. The effect of PGRsc on the enzyme activities involved in carbohydrate metabolism under salt stress is very complex and needs more investigation.

The results of this study showed that NaCl stress significantly decreased the soluble protein, soluble sugar and AsA in fruits. In plants, NaCl stress has a strong influence on nitrogen and carbon metabolism, and this is reflected in several changes occurring in a range of physiological and biochemical processes [70-72]. Plants can cope with salt stress by synthesizing such osmolytes as, soluble sugars, and protein, and the osmo-protectant activities such as AsA of these compounds have been well examined in higher plants [73, 74]. In our study using S3 induced soluble sugar in cucumber fruits. Sugars play a crucial role in plant metabolism. They supply carbon and energy, and can also participate in the signaling pathway initiating the up-regulation of defense-related genes and down-regulation of photosynthetic gene expression [75]. In a wide range of plants, total carbohydrate content increases after NaCl treatment, mainly due to elevated sugar (glucose and fructose), levels. There is strong evidence that glucose and fructose play a role during the relief period under various

conditions [3, 76].

Together, these results reveal that N metabolism is strongly interconnected with C metabolism. The use of fixed N for N assimilation needs to be coordinated with the C for carbohydrate synthesis. On the one hand, it is important to ensure that there is enough C diverted to produce C skeletons that are needed during the assimilation of N and the synthesis of amino acids [2]. Therefore, the C–N balance is important for plant growth and development. In this study, PGRsc could enhance the C flux toward the synthesis of sugars at the cost of N assimilation and thus control the C–N balance [77]. As a result, PGRsc could participate in the regulation of C and N assimilation, allowing plants to reach an optimal C–N ratio that will guarantee plant growth and development, resulting in a higher accumulation of biomass under stress conditions.

5. CONCLUSION

The results in this work indicate that exogenous 5 mM Put + 0.002 ppm mT + 0.001 ppm EBR to cucumber roots under salinity stress could up-regulate the levels of C–N enzymes activities involved in C–N metabolism. The significant effect of SPS and SS enzyme activities in turn could facilitate N assimilation with metabolic cost and C skeletons. In summary, the application of PGRsc (Put, mT and EBR) could help cucumber plants maintain equilibrium of C and N assimilation, which resulted in an improved NaCl tolerance, and eventually alleviated the inhibition of the growth caused by NaCl stress in cucumber plant.

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REFERENCES

1. Cui G, Zhang Y, Zhang W, Lang, D, Zhang X, Li Z, Zhang X. Response of carbon and nitrogen metabolism and secondary metabolites to drought stress and salt stress in plants. *J Plant Biol.* 2019; 62: 387-399.
2. Nunes-Nesi A, Fernie AR, Stitt M. Metabolic and signaling aspects underpinning the regulation of plant carbon nitrogen interactions. *Mol Plant.* 2010; 3: 973-996.
3. Liu C, Wang Y, Pan, K, Zhu T, Li W, Zhang LJ. Carbon and nitrogen metabolism in leaves and roots of dwarf bamboo (*Fargesia denudata* Yi) subjected to drought for two consecutive years during sprouting period. *J Plant Growth Regul.* 2014; 33: 243-255.
4. Zhu Y, Guo J, Feng R, Jia J, Han W, Gong HJ. The regulatory role of silicon on carbohydrate metabolism in *Cucumis sativus* L. under salt stress. *Plant Soil.* 2016; 406: 231-249.
5. El-Naggar ME, Abdelsalam NR, Fouda MM, Mackled MI, Al-Jaddadi MA, Ali HM, et al. Soil application of nano silica on maize yield and its insecticidal activity against some stored insects after the post-harvest. *Nanomaterials.* 2020; 10(4): 739.
6. Foyer CH, Noctor G, Verrier PJ. Photosynthetic carbon nitrogen interactions: modeling inter-pathway control and signaling. *Ann Plant Rev.* 2006; 22: 325-347.
7. Kandil EE, Abdelsalam NR, Mansour MA, Ali HM, Siddiqui MH. Potentials of organic manure and potassium forms on maize (*Zea mays* L.) growth and production. *Sci Rep.* 2020; 10: 1-11.
8. Kandil EE, Abdelsalam NR, El Aziz AaA, Ali HM, Siddiqui MH. Efficacy of nanofertilizer, fulvic acid and boron fertilizer on sugar beet (*Beta vulgaris* L.) yield and quality. *Sugar Tech.* 2020; 22: 782-791.

9. Shao Q, Shu S, Du J, Xing W, Guo S, Sun J. Effects of NaCl stress on nitrogen metabolism of cucumber seedlings. *Rus J Plant Physiol.* 2015; 62: 595-603.
10. Gomaa M, Kandil EE, El-Dein AA, Abou-Donia ME, Ali HM, Abdelsalam NR. Increase maize productivity and water use efficiency through application of potassium silicate under water stress. *Sci Rep.* 2021; 11: 1-8.
11. Rashad RT, Hussien RJ. A comparison study on the effect of some growth regulators on the nutrients content of maize plant under salinity conditions. *Ann Agricult Sci.* 2014; 59: 89-94.
12. Elmardy NA, Yousef AF, Lin K, Zhang X, Ali MM, Lamalom SF, Kalaji HM, Kowalczyk KM, Xu Y. Photosynthetic performance of rocket (*Eruca sativa*. Mill.) grown under different regimes of light intensity, quality, and photoperiod. *PLoS ONE* 16(9): e0257745.
13. Rademache WJ. Plant growth regulators: backgrounds and uses in plant production. *J Plant Growth Regul.* 2015; 34: 845-872.
14. Small CC, Degenhardt D. Plant growth regulators for enhancing re vegetation success in reclamation: A review. *Ecol Engin.* 2018; 118: 43-51.
15. Ferguson L, Grafton-Cardwell EE. *Citrus production manual.* UCANR Publications. 2014.
16. Flasiński M, Hąc-Wydro K. Natural vs synthetic auxin: Studies on the interactions between plant hormones and biological membrane lipids. *Environ Res.* 2014; 133: 123-134.
17. Choudhary SP, Bhardwaj R, Gupta B, Dutt P, Gupta R, Kanwar M, Biondi S. Enhancing effects of 24-epibrassinolide and Putrescine on the antioxidant capacity and free radical scavenging activity of *Raphanus sativus* seedlings under Cu ion stress. *Acta Physiol Plant.* 2011; 33: 1319-1333.
18. Sayed HA, Esraa AM, Weijie J, Basheer N , Hongjun Y, Peng L. Effect of different plant bio-stimulants in improving cucumber growth under soilless culture. *Eur J Biol Res.* 2021; 11: 146-155.
19. Wang L, Yang L, Yang F, Li X, Song Y, Wang X, Hu X. Involvements of H₂O₂ and metallothionein in NO-mediated tomato tolerance to copper toxicity. *J Plant Physiol.* 2010; 167(15): 1298-1306.
20. Hasan SA, Hayat S, Ali B, Ahmad A. 28Homobrassinolide Protects Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*) from Cadmium Toxicity by Stimulating Antioxidants. *Environ Poll.* 2008; 151: 60-66.
21. Bradford M. A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding *Anal Biochem.* 1976; 72: 248-254.
22. Ertani A, Sambo P, Nicoletto C, Santagata S, Schiavon M, Nardi S. The use of organic biostimulants in hot pepper plants to help low input sustainable agriculture. *Chem Biol Technol Agricult.* 2015; 2: 11.
23. Bremner JM. Nitrogen-Total, *Methods of Soil Analysis, Part 3. Chemical Methods.* 1996; <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssabookser5.3.c37>.
24. Xu J, Mohamed E, Li Q, Lu T, Yu H, Jiang WJ. Effect of humic acid addition on buffering capacity and nutrient storage capacity of soilless substrates. *Front Plant Sci.* 2021; 12: Article 644229.
25. Hernández J A, Almansa M. Short-term effects of salt stress on antioxidant systems and leaf water relations of pea leaves. *Physiol Plant.* 2002; 115(2): 251-257.
26. Wu X, He J, Chen J, Yang S, Zha D. Alleviation of exogenous 6-benzyladenine on two genotypes of eggplant (*Solanum melongena* Mill.) growth under salt stress. *Protoplasma.* 2014; 251: 169-176.
27. Khanam D, Mohammad F. Plant growth regulators ameliorate the ill effect of salt stress through improved growth, photosynthesis, antioxidant system, yield and quality attributes in *Mentha piperita* L. *Acta Physiol Plant.* 2018; 40:188.
28. Youssef MA, Yousef AF, Ali MM, Ahmed AI, Lamalom SF, Strobel WR, Kalaji HM. Exogenously applied nitrogenous fertilizers and effective microorganisms improve plant growth of stevia (*Stevia rebaudiana* Bertoni) and soil fertility. *AMB Express.* 2021; 11: 133.

29. Akter P, Rahman MA. Effect of foliar application of IAA and GA on sex expression, yield attributes and yield of bitter gourd (*Momordica Charantia* L.). *Chittagong Univ J Biol Sci.* 2010; 5(1): 55-62.
30. Schiavon M, Ertani A, Nardi S. Effects of an alfalfa protein hydro lysate on the gene expression and activity of enzymes of the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and nitrogen metabolism in *Zea mays* L. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2008; 56(24): 11800-11808.
31. Yuan L, Yuan Y, Du J, Sun J, Guo SJ. Effects of 24-epibrassinolide on nitrogen metabolism in cucumber seedlings under Ca (NO₃)₂ stress. *Plant Physiol Biochem.* 2012; 61: 29-35.
32. Chakrabarti N, Mukherji S. Effect of phytohormone pretreatment on nitrogen metabolism in *Vigna radiata* under salt stress. *Biol Plant.* 2003; 26: 63-66.
33. Nathawat N, Kuhad M, Goswami C, Patel A, Kumar R. Nitrogen-metabolizing enzymes: effect of nitrogen sources and saline irrigation. *Plant Nutr.* 2005; 28: 1089-1101.
34. Sairam R, Srivastav G, Agarwal S, Meena R. Differences in antioxidant activity in response to salinity stress in tolerant and susceptible wheat genotypes. *Biol Plant.* 2005; 49: 85-91.
35. Tang YY, Yuan YH, Shu S, Guo SRJSH. Regulatory mechanism of NaCl stress on photosynthesis and antioxidant capacity mediated by transglutaminase in cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) seedlings. *Scientia Horticult.* 2018; 235: 294-306.
36. Zhao J, Abdelsalam NR., Khalaf L, Chuang WP, Zhao L, Smith CM, et al. Development of single nucleotide polymorphism markers for the wheat curl mite resistance gene *Cmc4*. *Crop Sci.* 2019; 59: 1567-1575.
37. Zhao L, Liu S, Abdelsalam NR, Carver BF, and Bai G. Characterization of wheat curl mite resistance gene *Cmc4* in OK05312. *Theor Appl Gen.* 2021; 134: 993-1005.
38. Maathuis FJ. The role of monovalent cation transporters in plant responses to salinity. *J Exp Bot.* 2006; 57(5): 1137-1147.
39. Gorbe E, Calatayud AJSH. Applications of chlorophyll fluorescence imaging technique in horticultural research: A review. *Scientia Hortic.* 2012; 138: 24-35.
40. Demetriou G, Neonaki C, Navakoudis E, Kotzabasis K. Salt stress impact on the molecular structure and function of the photosynthetic apparatus-the protective role of polyamines. *Biochim Biophys Acta Bioenerg.* 2007; 1767: 272-280.
41. Yang L, Koo DH, Li Y, Zhang X, Luan F, Havey MJ, et al. Chromosome re arrangements during domestication of cucumber as revealed by high-density genetic mapping and draft genome assembly. *Plant J.* 2012; 71: 895-906.
42. Shi H, Ye T, Chan Z. Comparative proteomic and physiological analyses reveal the protective effect of exogenous polyamines in the bermudagrass (*Cynodon dactylon*) response to salt and drought stresses. *J Proteome Res.* 2013; 12(11): 4951-4964.
43. Prajapati S, Jamkar T, Singh O, Raypuriya N, Mandloi R, Jain PJPA. Plant growth regulators in vegetable production: An overview. *Plant Arch.* 2015; 10: 2582-8223.
44. Hu C, Zhao H, Shi J, Li J, Nie X, Yang GJ. Effects of 2, 4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid on cucumber fruit development and metabolism. *Int J Mol Sci.* 2019; 20(5): 1126.
45. Fontaine JX, Tercé-Laforgue T, Armengaud P, Clément G, Renou JP, Pelletier S, et al. Characterization of a NADH-dependent glutamate dehydrogenase mutant of *Arabidopsis* demonstrates the key role of this enzyme in root carbon and nitrogen metabolism. *Plant Cell.* 2012; 24: 4044-4065.
46. Lea PJ, Mifflin BJ. Nitrogen assimilation and its relevance to crop improvement. *Annual Plant Reviews book series,* 2018; 42.
47. Skopelitis DS, Paranychianakis NV, Paschalidis KA, Pliakonis ED, Delis ID, Yakoumakis DI, et al. Abiotic stress generates ROS that signal expression of anionic glutamate dehydrogenases to form glutamate for proline synthesis in tobacco and grapevine. *Plant Cell.* 2006; 18: 2767-2781.

48. Skopelitis DS, Paranychianakis NV, Kouvarakis A, Spyros A, Stephanou EG, Roubelakis-Angelakis K. The isoenzyme 7 of tobacco NAD (H)-dependent glutamate dehydrogenase exhibits high deaminating and low aminating activities in vivo. *Plant Physiol.* 2007; 145: 1726-1734.
49. Forde BG, Lea PJ. Glutamate in plants: metabolism, regulation, and signalling. *J Exp Bot.* 2007; 58(9): 2339-2358.
50. Labboun S, Tercé-Laforgue T, Roscher A, Bedu M, Restivo FM, Velanis CN, et al. Resolving the role of plant glutamate dehydrogenase. I. In vivo real time nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy experiments. *Plant Cell Physiol.* 2009; 50: 1761-1773.
51. Tonon G, Kevers C, Faivre-Rampant O, Graziani M, Gaspar TJ. Effect of NaCl and mannitol iso-osmotic stresses on proline and free polyamine levels in embryogenic *Fraxinus angustifolia* callus. *J Plant Physiol.* 2004; 161: 701-708.
52. Shi H, Chan ZJ. Improvement of plant abiotic stress tolerance through modulation of the polyamine pathway. *J Integr Plant Biol.* 2014; 56(2): 114-121.
53. Kishor PK, Sangam S, Amrutha R, Laxmi PS, Naidu K, Rao KS, et al. Regulation of proline biosynthesis, degradation, uptake and transport in higher plants: its implications in plant growth and abiotic stress tolerance. *Curr Sci.* 2005; 88: 424-438.
54. Slama I, Ghnaya T, Hessini K, Messedi D, Savoure A, Abdelly CJE, Botany E. Comparative study of mannitol and PEG osmotic stress effects on growth, proline and soluble sugars accumulation in *Sesuvium portulacastrum*. *Environ Exp Bot.* 2007; 61: 10-17.
55. Wang ZQ, Yuan YZ, Ou JQ, Lin QH, Zhang CF. Glutamine synthetase and glutamate dehydrogenase contribute differentially to proline accumulation in leaves of wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) seedlings exposed to different salinity. *J Plant Physiol.* 2007; 164: 695-701.
56. Pelleschi S, Rocher JP, Prioul J. Effect of water restriction on carbohydrate metabolism and photosynthesis in mature maize leaves. *Cell Environ.* 1997; 20: 493-503.
57. Li Z, Jing W, Peng Y, Zhang XQ, Ma X, Huang LK, Yan Y. Spermine alleviates drought stress in white clover with different resistance by influencing carbohydrate metabolism and dehydrins synthesis. *PLoS One.* 2015; 10(3): e0120708.
58. Abbas A, Shah AN, Shah AA, Nadeem MA, Alsaleh A, Javed T, et al. Genome-Wide Analysis of Invertase Gene Family, and Expression Profiling under Abiotic Stress Conditions in Potato. *Biology.* 2022; 11(4): 539.
59. Ahmad H, Zahid M, Rehan ZA, Rashid A, Akram S, Aljohani MM, et al. Preparation of Polyvinylidene Fluoride Nano-Filtration Membranes Modified with Functionalized Graphene Oxide for Textile Dye Removal. *Membranes.* 2022; 15:12(2): 224.
60. Akhtar G, Faried HN, Razzaq K, Ullah S, Wattoo FM, Shehzad MA, et al. Chitosan-Induced Physiological and Biochemical Regulations Confer Drought Tolerance in Pot Marigold (*Calendula officinalis* L.). *Agronomy.* 2022; 12(2): 474.
61. Abdelsalam NR, Balbaa MG, Osman HT, Ghareeb RY, Desoky ESM, Elshehawi AM, et al. Inheritance of resistance against northern leaf blight of maize using conventional breeding methods. *Saudi J Biol Sci.* 2022; 29(3): 1747-1759.
62. Abdelsalam NR, Grad WE, Ghura NS, Khalid AE, Ghareeb RY, Desoky ESM, et al. Callus induction and regeneration in sugarcane under drought stress. *Saudi J Biol Sci.* 2021; 28: 7432-7442.
63. Mendicino J. Sucrose phosphate synthesis in wheat germ and green leaves. *J Biol Chem.* 1960; 235: 3347-3352.
64. Naya L, Ladrera R, Ramos J, González EM, Arrese-Igor C, Minchin FR, Becana, M. The response of carbon metabolism and antioxidant defenses of alfalfa nodules to drought stress and to the subsequent recovery of plants. *Plant Physiol.* 2007; 144: 1104-1114.
65. Oufir M, Legay S, Nicot N, Van Moer K, Hoffmann L, Renaut J, et al. Gene expression in potato during cold exposure: changes in carbohydrate and polyamine metabolisms. *Plant Sci.* 2008; 175: 839-852.

66. Fresneau C, Ghashghaie J, Cornic G. Drought effect on nitrate reductase and sucrose-phosphate synthase activities in wheat (*Triticum durum* L.): role of leaf internal CO₂. *J Exp Bot.* 2007; 58: 2983-2992.
67. Gil R, Boscaiu M, Lull C, Bautista I, Lidón A, Vicente O. Are soluble carbohydrates ecologically relevant for salt tolerance in halophytes? *Funct Plant Biol.* 2013; 40: 805-818.
68. Richter JA, Erban A, Kopka J, Zörb C. Metabolic contribution to salt stress in two maize hybrids with contrasting resistance. *Plant Sci.* 2015; 233: 107-115.
69. Wei W, Li QT, Chu YN, Reiter RJ, Yu XM, Zhu DH, et al. Melatonin enhances plant growth and abiotic stress tolerance in soybean plant. *J Exp Bot.* 2015; 66: 695-707.
70. Ashraf M, Harris P. Potential biochemical indicators of salinity tolerance in plants. *Plant Sci.* 2004; 163: 3-16.
71. Abdelsalam NR. Marker assisted-selection of major traits in egyptian bread wheat (*triticum aestivum* L.) wild wheat (*aegilops ventricosa* tausch). *Plant Cell Biotechnol Mol Biol.* 2014; 15: 67-74.
72. Anjum SA, Ashraf U, Tanveer M, Khan I, Hussain S, Shahzad B, et al. Drought induced changes in growth, osmolyte accumulation and antioxidant metabolism of three maize hybrids. *Front Plant Sci.* 2017; 8: 69.
73. Muchate NS, Nikalje GC, Rajurkar NS, Suprasanna P, Nikam T. Plant salt stress: adaptive responses, tolerance mechanism and bioengineering for salt tolerance. *Bot Rev.* 2016; 82: 371-406.
74. Negrão S, Schmöckel S, Tester MJ. Evaluating physiological responses of plants to salinity stress. *Ann Bot.* 2017; 119: 1-11.
75. Gibson S. Plant sugar-response pathways. Part of a complex regulatory web. *Plant Physiol.* 2000; 124: 1532-1539.
76. Liu T, Van Staden JJ. Partitioning of carbohydrates in salt-sensitive and salt-tolerant soybean callus cultures under salinity stress and its subsequent relief. *Plant Growth Reg.* 2001; 33: 13-17.
77. Mattoo AK, Sobolev AP, Neelam A, Goyal RK, Handa AK, Segre AL. Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy-based metabolite profiling of transgenic tomato fruit engineered to accumulate spermidine and spermine reveals enhanced anabolic and nitrogen-carbon interactions. *Plant Physiol.* 2006; 142(4): 1759-1770.